

A Study on Service Quality of Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank in Thoothukudi Branch

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Abstract

In the present competitive economy banking sector has been facing dynamic challenges in concerning both customer base and performance. Providing service quality is highly significant function of service industry in today's competitive environment. In a new competitive scenario, service quality has become an important competitive tool. It is the excellent strategy and plays a key role in service sector in general and banking sector in particular to satisfy the customers' needs and retain them. TMB have played a major role in the development of financial service industry. For this purpose, 70 sample respondents of TMB account holders have been taken for the study. The primary data has been collected through well structured questionnaire by using random sampling method. The study conducted in Thoothukudi district only. The present study aims at assessing the service quality that delivered by the Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank, using SERVQUAL model.

Keywords: Service Quality, Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank, Banking services, Satisfaction.

Introduction

In the present competitive environment, consumers are increasingly aware of alternatives in relation to services and organizations providing services. Consequently, expectations rise and consumers become more critical of the quality of services. With a view to ensure efficient financial services, India has deregulated and liberalized the financial sector in general and the banking sector in particular. The Indian Banking System has witnessed significant transformation in recent years. Indian banks, before the institution of financial sector reforms, operated in a highly regulated environment with regard to different parameters, such as branch location, deposit and lending rates and deployment of credit, to mention a few. Further, in view of the social responsibility placed on the banking sector, profitability was not considered as an important yardstick of their performance.

Service Quality of the banks referred as an obligation of all banks to fulfill objectives and needs of customers. The present need of banks is to have good relationship with customers by providing quality services to retain existing and generate or acquire new customers. Thus, this study attempts to service quality in banking sector present scenario.

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SERVQUAL is one the tools used in measuring the quality of services. According to Buttle (1996), SERVQUAL is for the measuring and managing the quality of service. Asubeonteng et al (1996) also intimated that the model is used to measure the quality of service from the customer's point of view. The originators of the model are Parasuraman, Zeithamal and Berry. It was developed in 1985 but was polished in their subsequent articles (Parasuraman et al 1988). The main aim of SERVQUAL is to have a standard and a reliable tool that can be used to measure the quality of services in different service sectors. Originally, those who developed SERVQUAL introduced ten service quality dimensions or attributes. These are: 1. Tangibles, 2. Reliability, 3. Responsiveness, 4. Competency, 5. Courtesy, 6. Communication, 7. Credibility, 8. Security, 9. Access and 10. Understanding the customer.

Thus, the present study also Considers these five dimensions to assess the service quality of Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank in Thoothukudi branches. The five dimensions of SERVQUAL are

Tangibles: which pertain to the physical facilities, equipment, personnel and communication materials;

Reliability: This refers to the ability to perform the promised services dependably and accurately;

Responsiveness: which refers to the willingness of service providers to help customers and provide prompt service;

Assurance: This relates to the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to convey trust and confidence;

Empathy: This refers to the provision of caring and individualized attention to customers.

Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank

Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank Limited (TMB) is a bank headquartered at Thoothukudi, Tamil Nadu, India. TMB was founded in 1921 as the Nadar Bank, but changed its name to Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank in November 1962 to widen its appeal beyond the Nadar community. For the financial year 2016-2017, the bank reported a net profit of 3166 million. The bank currently has 509 full branches throughout India, 12 Regional offices and eleven Extension Counters, six central processing centres, one Service Branch, four Currency Chests, 19 eLobby centres and 1094 Automated Teller Machines (ATM). The bank has been expanding its footprint all over India.

TMB was rated as the fastest growing Private Sector Bank continuously for the five years from 2010 to 2015. It was also rated as the Best Bank in the years 2013, 2014 and 2015, due to its robust growth. During the years of 2016 and 2017 it did total business of 541 billion rupees. The bank's planned outlay for the financial year is to reach business worth 600 billion rupees, add an additional 24 branches, and increase its ATMs to 1150. The bank has won the Lokmat BFSI Best Private Sector Bank 2014-15 award.

Achievements

The Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank has a series of achievements and awards to its credit. In the Financial Year 2008-2009, the bank has received a few recognitions and appreciations. To begin with, the bank topped the list among 15 other banks in terms of performance in accordance to its Savings Bank Account in 2008. This was certified by a recognized agency of the Indian Banks Association. Apart from this; the Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank was also awarded the Dun & Bradstreet's Banking Awards for the best Indian Banks of the year 2009. The award was given for the private sector bank in the rural category.

Products & Services

Given below is a brief outline of the various services provided by the Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank:-

- Banking facility Anywhere Anytime
 - Demat A/c Services
 - Bill Payment Services
 - India Card Credit Card
 - RTGS, ECS & NEFT Service
 - NCDEX Clearing
 - Compensation Policy
 - Demat A/c Services
 - Bill Payment Services
- Mobile SMS Banking
 - Processing Charges
 - Smart Shoppers Visa Card
 - Mutual Fund Marketing
 - W.U. Money Transfer
 - Citizen's Charter
 - Mobile SMS Banking
 - Processing Charges

Review of Literature

Dr. A. Kavitha and M. Karthika¹(2018) in their research entitled on “A Study on Customers Service among Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank in Erode Branch” in this study revealed that the majority of banks are still successful in keeping with the confidence of the customer even though the main problems of the customer are not well aware of the service provided by their bank. In the process to attract customers these banks are providing highest level of service quality to satisfy the varying needs of today's customers.

Manimaran & V. Ramesh² (2015) in his study focused on “A Study on Service Quality Dimensions Assessment of Selected Private Banks In Tamilnadu State of India” in this study focused on the characteristics of banks and customer's expectation and perception on the services offered by banks, and the relationship between the profile of bank employees and their business performance.

Dr. E. Hari Prasad and Prof. G. V. Bhavani Prasad³(2017) in their research “Service Quality and Customers' Satisfaction in HDFC Bank” It is clear that there is significant difference in customers' opinions of HDFC in respect of the service quality. It requires the bank officials should more responsive and respond immediately to the queries and provide the needed information to the customers. It is conclude that the Bank needs to be more responsive and train its staff how to show empathy to their customers.

Dr. Kingshuk Adhikari and Dipankar Das⁴(2016) in this research Indicates that “Service Quality of Private Sector Banks: an empirical study” the study has adapted SERVPERF scale, keeping in view the locale of the study, to assess the service quality of three private sector banks by procuring perception of 120 bank customers through a field survey. It is concluded that better understanding of the perception of customers about different components of service quality.

Dr. C. Eugene Franco and G. Bright Jowerts⁵ (2017) in this research study on “Service Quality of Public and Private Sector Banks In Tirunelveli District” This study only focused on the dimensions of service quality i.e. reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy and responsiveness. The study sample has been stratified as 528 from public sector bank customers and 144 from private sector bank customers in Tirunelveli district. This study will pave way to further research to explore this mechanism in depth to provide quality banking services to facilitate the customers, the society and the economy as a whole.

Objectives of the Study

The study has the following objectives

1. To study the demographic profile of customers of Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank in Thoothukudi area.

2. To identify the service available to the customers at Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank in Thoothukudi branch.
3. Measurement of service quality in through SERVQUAL Model in the study area.
4. To give suggestions for improvement or change in the services of Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank.

Research Methodology

Primary Data

The methodology adopted for studying the objectives was surveying the saving account holders and structured questionnaire was adopted for the collection of primary data. A questionnaire has simple questions was devised and the respondents (Customers) were requested to answer these questions with correct information in branches of Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank in Thoothukudi branch. 70 respondents who are savings account in Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank in Thoothukudi city were selected for the study.

Secondary data

Secondary data has been collected through the various magazines and newspaper reports, documents, Banks annual reports , Internet other published information's.

Sampling Design

The personal judgment method has employed for the selection of banks, by using simple random method 70 customers has selected which is collected data based on researcher convenience methodology. This sample pack of 70 customers has duly calculated on the basis of sampling proportion.

Statistical Tools Used

- Simple Percentage Analysis
- Likert five point scale
- Ranking

Analysis and Interpretation

The demographic details of the selected sample respondents are given below.

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Number of Respondents N=70	Percentage
Age		
Below 25yrs	15	21.42
26-35yrs	20	28.57
36-45yrs	18	25.71
46-55yrs	10	14.28
Above 55yrs	7	10
Total	70	100
Gender		
Male	32	45.71
Female	38	54.28
Total	70	100
Marital Status		
Married	26	37.14

Single	44	62.85
Total	70	100
Educational Qualification		
Illiterate	8	11.42
School level	23	32.85
Degree/Diploma	14	20
Post Graduate	10	14.28
Professional degree	5	7.14
Others	10	14.28
Total	70	100
Monthly Income		
BelowRs.10,000	15	21.42
Rs.10001-20,000	22	31.42
Rs. 20,001- 30,000	19	27.14
Rs.30,001-40,000	8	11.42
aboveRs.40,000	6	8.57
Total	70	100
Occupation		
Govt, employee	10	14.28
Employee	32	45.71
Business	6	8.57
Professional	15	21.42
Others	7	10
Total	70	100
Family Status		
Nuclear family	44	62.85
Joint family	26	37.14
Total	70	100

Source: Primary data

The table 1 shows that demographic profile of the TMB customers which are taken for the study. Out of 70 respondents who were taken for the study: It has been identified that most(28.57%) whose age group is under 26-35years, (54.28%) of the respondents are female, (62.85%) of the respondents are single category, most (32.85%) of the respondents are school level, maximum number (45.71%) of respondents are employee, the monthly income of (31.42%) respondents is up to Rs.10001-20,000, (62.85%) of the respondents are Nuclear family.

Reason for Selection the TMB

Table 2 Reason for selection the TMB

S.No	Factors	Total Score	Mean Score	Rank
1.	Convenience	268	53.6	II
2.	Customer Service	280	56	I

3.	High Interest Rate	149	29.8	V
4.	Safety and Security	184	36.8	III
5.	Trust	169	33.8	IV

Source: Computed data

The table 2 shows the simple ranking method in respect of reason for selecting the TMB in study. It revealed that the majority of the respondents to give first rank for Customer service, followed by Convenience has been ranked as second, Safety and Security is ranked as third, Trust is ranked as fourth and High Interest Rate as fifth.

Serquel Dimensions of TMB

Table 3 SERQUEL dimensions of TMB

S.No.	Attributes	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total score
1.	Tangibility: The Bank must possess the sophisticated and good looking infrastructure.	25 (125)	7 (28)	16 (48)	14 (28)	8 (8)	237
2.	Reliability: The bank should provide service at the time it promises to do so.	29 (145)	17 (68)	8 (24)	10 (20)	6 (6)	263
3.	Responsiveness: The Bank employees should be always ready to respond to customers' requests.	17 (85)	15 (60)	18 (54)	14 (28)	6 (6)	233
4.	Assurance: The Bank employees always ought to be courteous and polite with customers.	15 (75)	25 (100)	13 (39)	7 (14)	10 (10)	238
5.	Empathy: The Bank operating hours must be convenient to all customers.	7 (35)	14 (56)	6 (18)	32 (64)	11 (11)	184

Source: Computed data

The table 3 shows the mean score of service quality of TMB about reliability dimension is the highest. So the customers are feel reliability services are gets first place, which is followed by assurance as second place, tangibility as third place, responsiveness as fourth place and empathy as fifth place of received service quality level of SERQUEL dimension.. Thus, with respect to dimensions of service quality, reliability may be considered as the best out of five dimensions considered in the study.

Suggestions

- The mean score of service quality of TMB about reliability dimension is the highest which is followed by assurance, empathy, responsiveness and tangibility dimension. So the TMB management to take necessary steps for improving service quality in assurance, empathy, responsiveness and tangibility dimension attributes.
- Majority of the respondents to selected TMB for better customer service. So the Tamilnadu mercantile banks further steps to take improve latest technologies in providing services.
- Most of the customers dissatisfied in the rate of interest. So TMB must be give better rate of interest for both savings and lending services.

Conclusion

Service quality should be used as a strategic tool to get a competitive advantage over the competitors. The SERQUEL model is used to assess the service quality of Tamilnadu mercantile Bank in Thoothukudi branch. In order to stay competitive the banks needs to improve on their service quality especially areas assurance, empathy, responsiveness and tangibility dimension which are major responsible factors for customer satisfaction.

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